

Research Article

Conceptual Design of Eduvillepreneur for Entrepreneurial Subjects

Diane Christine Fernandez¹ *, Junisaelah Naswar², Ainornazirah Abdul Ghani³, Amirah Abdul Raffar⁴, Siti Nor Fatin Ahmad Fodzi⁵, Hidayati Ahmad⁶, Nurul Aisyah Lau Huifen Mohd Ridwan Lau⁷ and Nurain Syamimi Haziqah Suparman⁸

- 1 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; diane@micost.edu.my; [0000-0001-7622-7840](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7622-7840)
2 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; junisaelah@micost.edu.my; [0009-0001-3568-1438](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3568-1438)
3 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; ainornazirah@micost.edu.my; [0009-0003-9372-4285](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9372-4285)
4 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; amirah@micost.edu.my; [0009-0006-1320-9032](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1320-9032)
5 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; norfatin@micost.edu.my; [0009-0003-2579-146X](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2579-146X)
6 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; hidayati@micost.edu.my; [0009-0004-0280-0113](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0280-0113)
7 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; nursyah777@gmail.com; [0009-0004-5485-1385](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5485-1385)
8 Melaka International College of Science and Technology; nurainsyamimi0602@gmail.com; [0009-0009-6664-569X](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6664-569X)
* Correspondence: diane@micost.edu.my.

Abstract: *Eduvillepreneur; a user interface (concept sketch prototype) has been generated in order to overcome the issue of passive lectures in entrepreneurship subjects in Malaysian Higher Educational Institutions. This project adapts the iterative process called design thinking initially developed by David Kelly. The process begins with “Empathize”, “Define”, “Ideate”, “Prototype” and “Test”. Brainstorming technique is used and then a prototype was generated using Canva App. Questionnaires were disseminated to 36 Diploma students that are taking entrepreneurship subjects. IBM SPSS Statistics Version 26 was utilized for analysis purposes. The interface designed using Canva App exclusively caters to students to do online business. The generic features are mostly catered for education purposes. There are three views which are Lecturer, Seller, and Customer. The highest mean value is 4.28 indicating that most of the respondents agree that Eduvillepreneur will help them in understanding entrepreneurial content. Eduvillepreneur interface can be commercialized through collaboration with any potential software developer. This interface is designed to be user-friendly and installed on any digital device. There are no online stores created solely for students taking entrepreneurship subjects in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions. By using this interface, students can engage with customers via online methods plus there are special features for lecturers to monitor and track students’ progress in utilizing this platform. The most significant impact will be on students as the Eduvillepreneur prepares students before going into the real business world through experience in dealing with customers via the online platform. This design layout of Eduvillepreneur could attract collaboration with software developers as well as the government in order to support the government’s efforts in producing more young entrepreneurs in Malaysia.*

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship; Technology-incorporated; Interactive Learning*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education in Malaysia has been implemented in numerous higher learning institutions as a component of entrepreneur subjects or even as an independent course (Bakar et al, 2022). Traditional teaching methods may be able in educating students regarding entrepreneurship and business techniques for success. However, they are incapable of developing the essential characteristics of entrepreneurs in students (Nian et al, 2014). A study conducted by Abdul Rahim (2020) suggested that the curriculum method of entrepreneurship subject may increase students' interest to become entrepreneurs. It was noted in a study by Ahmad & Buchanan (2015), passive lecturing was more prevalent in comparison to interactive approaches. Hence, it was advised in order to enhance entrepreneurship education effectively, Malaysian universities should address these matters. Moreover, arising with the pandemic has resulted in students becoming interested in technology (Othman et al, 2022). Thus, an idea for designing a user interface (*concept sketch prototype*) has been generated by the team members in order to overcome the issue of passive lectures in entrepreneurship subject.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this innovation project is adapting the iterative process called design thinking originally developed by David Kelly. The process begins with "Empathize", "Define", "Ideate", "Prototype" and "Test" (Reilly & Binns, 2019). At the empathize and define stage, a literature review was conducted to understand the teaching method and style for entrepreneurial subjects and the importance of technology-incorporated activities. Next, the team brainstorm to find alternative methods to address the gap via the ideate stage. Upon completion of conceptualizing the design, a concept sketch prototype was generated utilizing the Canva App (*Refer to Appendix 1*). For the test stage, questionnaires (*Refer to Appendix 2*) were disseminated to participants to attain students' perception towards the effectiveness of Eduvillepreneur conceptual design as a platform for students selling their products for Entrepreneurial subjects. The scale was analysed with five items modified from Cheung & Ng (2021). IBM SPSS Statistics Version 26 was utilized for analysis purposes.

2.1 Innovation Background

The conceptual design of Eduvillepreneur focuses on Business field students in higher education institutions. The idea of the interface is exclusively for students to showcase their products for selling purposes. Like an online store but features catered for education purposes. There are three views, (1) Lecturer, (2) Seller, (3) Customer.

Table 1. Features based on lecturer, seller and customer

View	Features
Lecturer	Lecturers will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register students who enrolled in Entrepreneur subject via Eduvillepreneur • Decide the categorisation of product category by adding/removing/renaming • Evaluate students
Seller (Student)	Students will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register store • Add products • Manage Orders • Reviews and respond to customers' feedback
Customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two options: Staff/students and external customer

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff/students- drop off at campus • External customers- cash on delivery, e-wallet payment, delivery fee • Chat feature to seller on inquiry • Customer reviews and rating
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Source: The authors.

3. FINDINGS

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Statement 1	4.08	0.732
Statement 2	4.28	0.701
Statement 3	4.17	0.697
Statement 4	4.19	0.668
Statement 5	4.06	0.630

Source: The authors.

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation scores for each statement that has been asked in the survey. The highest mean value is 4.28 indicating that all the respondents agree that Eduvillepreneur will help them in understanding entrepreneurial content. Overall, it shows that the respondents believe with the usage of Eduvillepreneur may help them enhance their learning performance. The standard deviation scores for all the statements are well below 1.00, indicating that the respondents are clustered around the mean (Teoh, Chong, Lin & Chua, 2013).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Commercialization Potential of Eduvillepreneur Design

Eduvillepreneur interface (concept sketch prototype) can be commercialized through collaboration with any potential software developer. The idea can be used to generate Entrepreneurship educational software with the help of IT specialists. The potential market segment for Eduvillepreneur is higher learning institutions which offer Entrepreneurship subjects. Higher learning institutions may include Eduvillepreneur in the curriculum method which helps lecturers achieve active learning in the class as Roberts (2019) suggests that students’ involvement in data collection and problem-solving is crucial. The interface can be designed as an app that can be installed through any digital device such as laptops, tablets as well as smartphones. Easy access to the system for both students and lecturers will maximise teaching and learning performance.

4.2 Novelty of Eduvillepreneur Design

As our world is moving towards a virtual world, the involvement of students at universities in entrepreneurial activities is vital to ensure they are able to face the competitive environment. Online shops/stores are one of the methods for assessment tools that may test the student’s ability to handle their business and their ability to create suitable products that meet customer desires. Currently, based on authors’ awareness, even though in Malaysia there are many types of online stores, for instance Lazada, Shopee, and TikTok Shop, there are no online stores created exclusively for students taking entrepreneurship subjects in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions. Furthermore, with this interface, students can also learn how to engage with customers and apply it later on in future. Taking this into consideration, this innovation will help lecturers provide a fair assessment as they are able to monitor and track students’ progress in utilizing this platform for selling purposes.

4.3 Impact of the Innovation Project

The major impact of our project would be on the students, as they are the ones who will be taking entrepreneurial subjects. In terms of the students, this project is an efficient solution for promoting interaction between students and the curriculum, increasing students' engagement with learning about entrepreneurship. It can also boost their motivation to develop their entrepreneurial skills. In this design of Eduvillepreneur, students can get a wide view of how the real world of managing business would be conducted, and indirectly, they are preparing themselves before going into the business world. This allows students to have the experience of choosing and creating products as a seller, determining the appropriate price for the product, and getting feedback from customers. Nevertheless, this interactive user interface would have an impact on the educational institution as well, where they could promote to the students how interesting the subject is and open up new opportunities for collaborating with IT organisations and other parties involved in developing the project.

5. CONCLUSION

Considering all of these, the existence of the design layout of Eduvillepreneur may assist students in preparing for their assessment that relates to the entrepreneur subject. Apart from that, it helps students apply knowledge and gain a better understanding of entrepreneurial subjects. It also increases students' skills in creating and using online business platforms as their tools to promote products. Practically, this innovation enhances the student's learning performance where they can acquire better entrepreneurial knowledge that can be implemented in the future for selling their product. Alternatively, in terms of commercialization potential, this design layout of Eduvillepreneur could attract collaboration with software developers in Malaysia as well as to promote to other institutions that have entrepreneurship subjects. In conclusion, this innovation also creates more opportunities to collaborate with the government in order to support the government's efforts in producing more young entrepreneurs in Malaysia.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Concept Sketch Prototype of Eduvillepreneur.

Source: The authors

Appendix 2. Students' perception towards the effectiveness of Eduvillepreneur conceptual design questionnaire

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1.	In my opinion, the use of Eduvillepreneur will enable me to better prepare for the assessments.					
2.	In my opinion, the use of Eduvillepreneur will enable me to understand entrepreneurial contents.					
3.	In my opinion, the use of Eduvillepreneur will allow me to apply knowledge.					
4.	In my opinion, by using Eduvillepreneur, I will be able to learn easily.					
5.	In my opinion, using Eduvillepreneur will enhance my learning performance.					

Note: 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, 5- strongly agree

Source: Adapted from Cheung & Ng (2021).